

CONTINUUM DAMAGE MECHANICS MODELLING OF A 3D PRINTED CURVILINEAR CFRTP

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ABSTRACT

Continuum damage mechanics was applied to a 3D printed curvilinear carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (c-CFRTP) to predict mechanical response due to loading. The material model was developed by means of finite element analysis, in which user-defined material subroutine was implemented. Elasto-plastic behavior of the 3D printed c-CFRTP including damage initiation and propagation was identified by a monotonic and cyclic tensile tests of the three specimens, i.e. $[(\pm 45)_2]_s$, $[(0/90)_2]_s$ and $[(\pm 67.5)_2]_s$ specimens. Then, the 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP was tested in monotonic tensile loading. Non-linear mechanical behavior of the 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP due to plasticity and damage initiation and propagation due to tensile loading was well predicted by the numerical simulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

3D printing enables fabrication of near-net-shape complex three-dimensional (3D) parts without expensive moulds or tools if one only has 3D CAD (Computer aided design) data [1-3]. Although there are several types of 3D printing systems, a 3D printer based on fused deposition molding (FDM) technique has been widely using because of the simple structure and usability. A continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (c-CFRTP) can also be 3D-printed by using the FDM technique.

In the FDM-based 3D printer, continuous carbon fibers and thermoplastic resin are ejected (or withdrawn) from the nozzle, and the print path is equivalent to the local reinforcement direction in the printed material. Therefore, 3D data-based 3D printing, i.e., direct digital manufacturing, makes a c-CFRTP that is more optimized in tow-level orientation [4]. Net-shape manufacturing is also an advantage of 3D printing, which reduces carbon fiber waste in the processing. 3D printing promotes multiproduct manufacturing by suppling a variety of 3D data to one 3D printer because of the out-of-mould manufacturing.

Curvilinear path can print since the 3D printer uses thin filament (filament diameter is generally less than 0.5 mm) which can be bended by heating in the nozzle. Therefore, a 3D-complicate shape can be fabricated by using c-CFRTP. However, mechanical property of a 3D-printed c-CFRTP is inherently low due to the process induced defect [5-8]. There are many weld-lines in a 3D printed part with relatively large voids between the c-CFRTP filaments and within the filament. These are inherent defects for a 3D printed c-CFRTP parts.

A 3D printed c-CFRTP part will be applied to structural parts, which should carry operational load. Durability analysis of the 3D printed c-CFRTP parts needs to be required to assure the structural reliability. In this study, continuum damage mechanics was applied to the 3D printed c-CFRTP to predict the mechanical property and damage evolution due to loading.

2 3D PRINTING OF C-CFRTP PARTS

An FDM based 3D printer (MarkTwo, Markforged) was used to print c-CFRTP. The filament provided by Markforged consists of continuous carbon fibers and nylon resin [5, 7] and was used as it is. The fiber volume fraction is about 30 % which is measured by cross-sectional observation [5]. The

diameter of the filament is about 0.4 mm. Nylon filament (without carbon fiber reinforcement) is not used in this study although it is required to print at the first and the last layer of the printed part as default. The nylon filament was intentionally not supplied to the printer, and the clearance between nozzle tip and printer-bed was adjusted appropriately without the thickness of first nylon layer. Therefore, the 3D printed specimens for measurement of the mechanical and damage properties were printed using only the c-CFRTP filament.

3 CHARACTERIZATION OF 3D PRINTED C-CFRTP

Continuum damage mechanics was applied to characterize the 3D printed c-CFRTP [9, 10]. The mechanical behavior such as elasticity, plasticity and damage evolution were identified by a monotonic and cyclic tensile testing of 3D printed c-CFRTP specimens of three stacking sequences. Rectangular coupons of $[(\pm 45)_2]_s$, $[(0/90)_2]_s$, $[(\pm 67.5)_2]_s$ lamination were 3D printed, and the mechanical testing were performed. Figure 1 shows a 3D printed c-CFRTP coupon specimen. End-tabs made of glass fiber reinforced plastic were adhered after 3D printing of the coupon specimen using epoxy adhesive.

Commercially available finite element code (Abaqus 6.14) was used for numerical simulation. Continuum damage mechanics based material model was developed by user subroutine UMAT. Return Mapping Algorithm was applied to fit the nonlinear behavior of the materials. Elasto-plastic property and damage properties of the 3D printed c-CFRTP were identified followed by previous reports [9, 10]. The materials properties obtained were summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1: 3D printed c-CFRTP coupon specimen.

Table 1: Mechanical property and damage parameters of the 3D printed c-CFRTP.

Parameter	Value
Elasticity	
Longitudinal Young's Modulus E_1	57.8 GPa
Transverse Young's Modulus E_2	2.30 GPa
In-plane Shear Modulus G_{12}	1.56 GPa
In-plane Major Poisson's ratio ν_{12}	0.490
Plasticity	
Yield Stress R_0	10 MPa
Hardening Parameter β	305 MPa
Hardening Multiplier α	0.618
Coupling Parameter a	0.450
Damage	
Shear Damage Coefficient c_1	0.279
Shear Damage Intercept c_2	0.304
Transverse Damage Coefficient c_1'	0.386
Transverse Damage Intercept c_2'	0.344
Coupling Parameter b	2.47

4 VALIDATION OF THE DAMAGE MODEL USING A 3D PRINTED CURVILINEAR C-CFRTP

4.1 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP specimen

A 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP specimen was 3D printed using the same c-CFRTP filament to validate the mechanical and damage model obtained in the previous section. Fig. 2 shows 3D printing of a curvilinear c-CFRTP, and Fig. 3 shows the 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP. The 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP was cut into two to obtain two specimens (Fig. 4). Continuous carbon fibers were aligned along to the specimen edge. Fiber direction was unidirectional but was waved according to the specimen shape. The maximum fiber orientation angle of the specimen is 30 degrees at the longitudinal center of the specimen, and the orientation angle changes continuously along the longitudinal direction. End-tabs of glass fiber reinforced plastic were adhered after 3D printing of the specimen to grip in the tensile test.

4.2 Tensile test

Tensile test of the 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP specimen was performed with a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min using a universal testing machine (AG-IS, Shimadzu). Three strain gages were adhered on a specimen surface to measure x -directional (axial) strain in the test.

Figure 2: 3D printing of a curvilinear c-CFRTP.

Figure 3: 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP

(Two specimens were obtained by cutting into two)

4.3 Finite element analysis

The mechanical behaviour of the 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP specimen was numerically simulated by means of finite element analysis (Abaqus/Standard Ver.6.14). The developed material model in Section 3 was implemented using UMAT. The analytical model is shown in Fig. 5. Material property was assigned to all the elements after coordinate transformation since the fiber orientation angle was continuously changed along the longitudinal direction. Assuming that damage was consistent through the thickness direction of the specimen, the number of the elements along the thickness direction was 1. The element type was linear brick element (C3D8) with the size of $1 \times 1 \times 2$ mm. The total number of nodes was 8694. One end was fixed and tensile displacement was applied at the another end. Out-of-plane displacement was constrained in order to prevent rigid-body motion. Incremental iterative solution procedure was applied under displacement control. The initial stiffness method was adopted, in which tangent stiffness matrix was not updated.

4.3 Results of numerical simulation and comparison to the experiments

Mechanical behavior of the 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP specimen under tensile loading was numerical simulated. Fig. 6 shows x -directional strain in the specimen. Strains were localized in the specimen due to the curvilinear shape. Damage evolution was also localized in the specimen.

The relation between axial force and axial strains at each location obtained by experiment and numerical simulation were compared in Fig. 7. Nonlinear behavior of the specimen due to damage evolution was reasonably estimated by the numerical simulation. It was shown that continuum damage mechanic can be applied to the 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP to predict the mechanical behavior.

Figure 4: 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP specimen.

Figure 5: Analytical model.

Figure 6: Contour plot of x -directional strain obtained by numerical simulation.

Figure 7: Axial force and longitudinal strain curves obtained by experimental and simulation on tensile loading of the 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP specimen at three locations.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The material model was developed based on CDM and finite element analysis was performed to numerically simulate nonlinear mechanical behavior of the 3D-printed curvilinear c-CFRTP under monotonic tensile loading. It was shown that the elasto-plastic behavior and the damage behavior were identified using three type of rectangle shape specimens i.e. $[(0/90)_2]_s$, $[(\pm 45)_2]_s$ and $[(\pm 67.5)_2]_s$ specimens. Stress-strain response of the 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP specimen in the tensile loading was predicted and compared with the experimental results. It was shown that the non-linear behavior of the 3D printed curvilinear c-CFRTP in the tensile loading was well predicted using the finite element analysis considering the CDM based material model.

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